

ETHICAL STANDARDS IN NURSING ACTIVITY

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“Tibbiyotda xorijiy tili” fani o'qituvchi

ANNOTATION

In this article, a modern nurse should be able to identify the mental and social problems caused by the disease, and should be able to direct all the forces of the society to eliminate these problems, and should learn the art of communicating with the patient in such a way. It should be noted that he should help the patient to get out of the vortex of illness with his sweet words and gentle treatment, so the rules of ethics were violated.

Key words: Nurse, ethics, morality, patient, duty, value, happiness

In order to provide high-level medical services to the population, medical personnel with deep knowledge and a qualified outlook are required. of society development while this to the need necessity strengthened . At first to the nurse of the doctor instructions executor simple performer as the blacks was Current nurses , patients maintenance according to independent direction have being nursing science development contributions additions need and adding they are coming Modern a nurse medical procedures technique do it to know with together with the patient disease because of surface came and coming possible was , spiritual , social problems determine take and in society all forces this to problems eliminate to do towards take need and the patient with to communicate access art so take over it must be sweet the word is soft treatment with to the

patient illness from the vortex to escape help give take it Time requirements according to of the nurse activity to show circle , to them in organizational , pedagogic directions the work take to go , demand is being done . Nursing of work essence centuries during society requirements and of people to live conditions looking changed went

In 1859 , F. Nightingale " Care about in the book " memories ". nursing 1 per job scientific accuracy entered Nursing work this the patient healing in order to his around from the environment is to use that counts . Nursing from care target , patient own strength activation for to him comfortable conditions from creating consists of , i.e to the patient freedom , freedom , purity air , right eating organize to do means is caught .

Profession ethics of nursing moral aesthetic and intellectual characteristics .

The word **ethics** from Greek - ethos from the word received being , walking , standing , morality said meanings means Morality when you say of people to each other relation to society , state , country , family has been relationship is understood .

Moral concepts - to these duty , responsibility , dignity , conscience , honor and happiness concepts enters

Duty - medicine employee duty humanity manifestation do , has always to the patient help show , of people spiritual and physical to health against focused , they to his life risk puter hattin - in actions not participating

Liability-medicine nurse own duty in execution saranjom blonde to be , to feel the responsibility , profession over consumption not to do own in charge of task full excellent in fulfillment of the degree is expressed .

Honor - the concept consciousness , own reputation and fame , own value to keep it is said .

Dignity is occupation dignity , work qualification always to increase has been constant is an aspiration .

Conscience - person's moral concept , honesty , truthfulness , justice and moral purity own profession and others rights respect is to do

Happiness - happy life concept health from the concept is inseparable . Health good otherwise , complete of happiness to be possible it's not . Medicine employee behavior morality problems see exit on time main and common issues separately separate show can General from issues conditional respectively their two of them separate show can

- **Internal culture to the rules** to work right attitude , discipline , community property caution with to look at , without advice the work to see and solidarity feelings enters

- **External behavior to the rules** manners , politeness and belongs to external view to the rules compliance from doing consists of cleanliness , shoes , clothes cleanliness , excess ornaments and make up not to be , white robe , arm bag and the work of forms to be)

Medicine nurse population with the work take will go in itself moral , aesthetic and intellectual signs form take and mother that's it characters the owner to be need

- **Nurse's moral signs** simplicity , endurance , honesty , delicacy , politeness , open volunteering , cuteness , kindness .

- Nurse's Aesthetic signs - simplicity , modesty , openness modesty , in the hospital ok mood create to get enters

- Intellectual signs - knowledge observation , insight , self of your profession master to be enters

Of the disease internal essence

The patient sickness feeling , health changes differentiate knowledge , eye to the front cause , disease the reason realize reach , treatment diagnosis to treatments

approach-generalized without of the disease internal essence about concepts means That's it to understanding have or have that it is not to account taken patients two to the category is divided .

1. **Positive to look at have has been people** , disease internal essence understand , own to health right in relation divisor patients .

2. **Disease internal essence not understanding** to health wrong in relation divisor patients-negative to look at have has been people - 1 - category patients a nurse ordered everyone tasks full shed which performs and treatment diagnosis to work help they give Second category patients while a nurse the work in the activity difficulty giving birth treatment to the process harm deliver , they the following to the characters are divided .

1) **Negative** - you are not satisfied in relation those who

2) **Ignore it** - in health they recognize the disease but it is necessary measures compliance they do n't

3) **Giveable** - they worthless to changes excess given , own diseases with busy will be

4) **Hypochondriac** in relation to be a patient disease out of panic depressed fall , changes bulging they show

5) **Utilities** are a disease behind both material and spiritual interest they look

To ethics special concepts and of nurses task

Patients with the work take on the go nurse , patients between to be some concepts to the essence attention with to look necessary They are the following :

- **Egogeny** - the patient disease because of to himself effect it is negative and positive will be Nurse to the patient always positive can influence it is necessary

- **Egratogeny** - patients mutually to each other effect

- **Iatrogenic** - medicine employees wrong even actions as a result come coming out in the patient to the situation it is said . Of this as a result come coming out disease iatrogenic disease that is called To them the following reason will be :

- 1) Illness diagnosis and the results rush with to them known to do
- 2) Treatment diagnosis treatments wrong perform explanation
- 3) Employees irresponsibility .
- 4) Hospitalism - the patient hospital and his to the conditions until

it fits has been time

Used books :

MA Fozilbekova , NA Nurmatova . " Nursing work theoretical basics ". TY Umarova .

IA Kayumova . "Nursing work".

Q.S. Inomov . " Nursing work basics ".

